

UNIFOOD CONFERENCE

University of Belgrade

Book of Abstracts

Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021

CIP - Kategorizacija u publikaciji Narodna biblioteka Srbije, Beograd

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

663/664(048)

UNIFOOD conference (2021 ; Beograd)

Program i zbornik radova = Book of Abstracts / Unifood conference, Belgrade, September 24-25, 2021 ; [editors Mirjana Pešić, Živoslav Tešić].

- Belgrade : University of Belgrade, 2021 (Beograd : Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva TMF).
- 197 str. ; 30 cm

Tiraž 30.

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

a) Храна - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 47517705

UNIFOOD Conference, Belgrade September 24-25 2021

Book of Abstracts

Published by

University of Belgrade
Studentski trg 1
11000 Belgrade
www.bg.ac.rs,
email: kabinet@rect.bg.ac.rs

For Publisher

Ivanka Popović, rector

Editors

Mirjana Pešić
Živoslav Tešić

Cover Design Layout

Ivana Isaković

Circulation

30

ISBN 978-86-7522-066-4

Print

Razvojno-istraživački centar Grafičkog inženjerstva
Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Karnegijeva 4, Belgrade

Published

2021.

UNIFood2021 Conference

24th-25th September 2021 University of Belgrade

2nd International UNIFood Conference

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The word of welcome

Dear colleagues,

We would like to welcome you to the **2nd UNIFood International Conference –UNIFood2021**. We hope that this gathering will engage not only academics, but also the stakeholders from all the relevant industries and business sectors, serving as a meeting point and a platform for proliferation of new ideas and development of new partnerships.

The first UNIFood conference, organized as national, was established 2018. year as one of the events in honor of the **210th Anniversary** celebration of the **University of Belgrade** that ranked at Shanghai list on 35th place for the 2017 year in subject *Food Science and Technology*. The University of Belgrade has been recognized as a leading international scientific institution by LERU when it was selected to be a member of CE7, an informal network of seven Central and Eastern European universities collaborating with LERU on key research and education challenges. Furthermore, University of Belgrade joined European University Alliance Circle U. Following the European Commission's launch of the European Universities initiative, a group of research-intensive universities has entered into a Memorandum of Understanding with the intention of establishing a new university alliance: Aarhus University, Humboldt University of Berlin, King's College London, UC Louvain, University of Belgrade, University of Oslo and Université de Paris.

We are pleased that you have decided to take part in this mutual conversation, where many will present their recent work, through poster sessions, oral communications or simply by asking questions. One of the goals of this Conference is cooperation between academia and food industry. Food scientists, technologists, researchers, nutritionists, engineers and entrepreneurs will exchange their knowledge about the latest advances in all aspects of food production, processing, sustainability, safety and security, nutrition and health, hi-tech equipment, ethics and knowledge transfer supporting environment. At this meeting, over 200 participants from 23 countries will take part.

Belgrade, one of the oldest city in the Europe, always young, at the confluence of the Sava and Danube rivers, will be your host. At the confluence of new ideas and experiences we again wish you a warm welcome.

Sincerely,

Prof. Dr Mirjana Pešić

*President of the Scientific Committee
of UNIFood2021*

Prof. Dr Ivanka Popović

Rector of the University of Belgrade

BILE ACIDS – A PHARMACO-NUTRACEUTICAL APPROACH

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Due to amphipathic properties, bile acids (BAs), a major constituent of the bile, have several physiological functions including solubilization and absorption of dietary lipids and lipophilic xenobiotics, solubilization of cholesterol in bile, stimulation of bile flow and biliary phospholipid secretion and cholesterol excretion. BAs also have antibacterial properties, significantly influencing the composition of intestinal bacterial flora and maintaining the sterility of the biliary tree. The aim of this study was to summarize the present knowledge in the innovative field of BAs pharmacology, to reveal novel mechanisms of their action, focusing on clinically-relevant aspects. A detailed and comprehensive search of PubMed and Scopus databases was carried out for original and review articles. Initial mainly mechanistic function of BAs has been expanded to diverse and versatile regulatory functions involving cell homeostasis, hepatic and extra-hepatic metabolic processes, regulation of cell proliferation and death, and carcinogenesis. BAs are now recognized as signaling molecules capable to activate specific nuclear and membrane receptors, multiple cellular kinase signaling pathways. BAs can directly and through epigenetic mechanisms regulate the expression of genes involved in integrative metabolism and homeostasis. Disturbances in BA homeostasis contribute to the development of intestinal dysbiosis, dyslipidemia, obesity, inflammatory diseases, common metabolic diseases such as diabetes, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease, liver cirrhosis, hepatobiliary and intestinal disorders, carcinogenesis, even the disorders of the central nervous system. The field of research of natural and semisynthetic derivatives of BAs and BA-receptors ligands has been extensively expanding and several BA-based therapeutics have been approved for the treatment of liver and intestinal diseases. These biomolecules may also influence drug bioavailability and metabolism, by interacting with nuclear receptor-transcriptional networks, the expression of membrane transport proteins and drug-metabolizing enzymes. Bile acids can be utilized in the formulation of conventional dosage forms, but also of novel micellar, vesicular and polymer-based therapeutic systems.

Keywords: metabolic syndrome, nuclear receptor, microflora, inflammation, carcinogenesis

Acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia, project no. 41012.